

Ça y est : Annotating Arabic Texts for Teaching

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ABSTRACT (ENGLISH)

This paper critically examines the use of digital tools for processing contemporary Arabic texts from a pedagogical perspective. Through a case study, it explores the challenges arising in the digitization, OCR, and linguistic annotation of texts characterized by graphic variation, register alternation, and code-switching. By combining generative OCR, automatic annotation following the Universal Dependencies framework, and manual validation in the INCEpTION environment, the study shows how errors and annotative ambiguities reveal the limits of existing standards and can be reframed as pedagogical resources. The paper thus argues for a critical approach to Arabic digital textuality as a space of mediation between linguistic complexity and computational practices.

Keywords: Arabic digital textuality; OCR; morphosyntactic parsing; Universal Dependencies; Arabic language teaching

ABSTRACT (ITALIANO)

Ça y est : Annotare testi arabi per la didattica. Il contributo analizza criticamente l'applicazione di strumenti digitali al trattamento di testi arabi contemporanei in una prospettiva orientata alla didattica. A partire da un caso di studio, vengono esaminate le principali criticità che emergono nelle fasi di digitalizzazione, OCR e annotazione linguistica di testi caratterizzati da variazione grafica, alternanza di registri e *code-switching*. Attraverso una pipeline che integra OCR generativo, annotazione automatica secondo lo schema *Universal Dependencies* e validazione manuale in ambiente INCEpTION, il lavoro mostra come errori e ambiguità annotative non costituiscano semplici rumori, ma rendano visibili i limiti degli standard esistenti e possano essere valorizzati come risorse didattiche. Il contributo propone quindi una riflessione sulla testualità digitale araba come spazio di mediazione tra complessità linguistica reale e strumenti computazionali.

Parole chiave: testualità digitale araba; OCR; parsing morfosintattico; Universal Dependencies; didattica dell'arabo

1. INTRODUCTION¹

The teaching of Arabic at the university level is characterized by a marked heterogeneity of approaches, learning objectives, and disciplinary traditions. Arabic language courses are situated within different academic pathways, including linguistic, literary, historical and cultural studies, or area studies, giving rise to pedagogical models that may privilege the acquisition of communicative competence, formal linguistic analysis, the reading and interpretation of literary texts, or a combination of these dimensions. While this plurality represents a scientific and pedagogical asset, it also complicates the design of shared teaching tools and resources capable of addressing diverse educational needs without flattening their specificities. Within this fragmented landscape, the text, understood both as literary and non literary, continues to occupy a central position. Textual materials constitute the primary means of access to Arabic language, culture, and discursive practices, and play a crucial role in the teaching of language as well as literature and culture. However, authentic texts are rarely used in teaching contexts, especially in the early stages of acquisition, as they often display a level of linguistic complexity that reflects structural features of contemporary Arabic, such as orthographic variation, the coexistence of registers and varieties, and the use of code-switching, elements that are difficult to reconcile with fully standardized linguistic models. Moreover, this textual complexity frequently comes into tension with the digital tools currently available for the analysis and automatic processing of Arabic, which tend to presuppose a

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normalized and relatively homogeneous language. In particular, Optical Character Recognition (OCR) technologies and linguistic annotation systems show significant limitations when applied to texts that diverge from standard varieties or that exhibit linguistic and graphic hybridity. The result is a gap between the linguistic reality of the materials actually used in teaching and the digital resources that can be employed to support their analysis, mediation, and reuse.

It is precisely within this space of friction between the real linguistic complexity of texts and digital tools that both the RĀBIṬA project² and the reflection developed in this contribution are situated, with the aim of critically examining the potential and limitations of computational practices applied to Arabic texts from a pedagogically oriented perspective. Through a case study, we present the obstacles encountered and the solutions identified at different stages of text processing, from the transformation of printed material into digital form to the open access provision of teaching materials designed to support courses in Arabic language, culture, history, and literature.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

In recent years, the field of Digital Humanities has devoted increasing attention to the computational study of texts, developing methodologies and tools for the analysis, representation, and annotation of literary corpora. However, much of this reflection has focused on European textual traditions or on languages characterized by relative graphic and normative stability. In non European contexts, and particularly for languages with complex writing systems and strong internal variation, the application of models and tools developed elsewhere raises theoretical and methodological questions that have only been partially explored (Fiormonte, Chaudhuri and Ricaurte, 2022). In the case of Arabic, digital textuality is confronted with a series of structural challenges related to the nature of the writing system, orthographic variability, and the coexistence of registers and linguistic varieties (Alayba, 2025). The literature has extensively documented the difficulties encountered by OCR technologies when applied to Arabic texts, especially in the presence of non-standardized printed editions, heterogeneous fonts, or materials that reflect hybrid linguistic practices (Alghyaline, 2023). Errors produced during the recognition phase are not limited to simple graphic inaccuracies, but significantly affect the morphosyntactic structure of the text, compromising the quality of subsequent stages of automatic processing. These issues are compounded by those related to linguistic annotation and the adoption of shared standards such as Universal Dependencies (UD). Although such standards represent a fundamental reference point for computational linguistics, their application to Arabic texts characterized by variation, code-switching, or other contact phenomena raises important questions (Saadiyeh et al., 2025; Gaser et al., 2023; Riabi, Sagot and Seddah, 2021). The tension between the need for normalization and fidelity to the linguistic reality of the text emerges particularly clearly in contexts where variation is not noise to be eliminated, but a constitutive feature of the linguistic data. While these aspects have been widely discussed in computational and linguistic research, less attention has been devoted to their implications in teaching contexts. In particular, the way in which the challenges of Arabic digital textuality, from OCR to annotation, can be integrated into a pedagogical reflection that takes into account the plurality of approaches to teaching Arabic and the central role of the text as an object of mediation remains largely underexplored.

3. FROM PAGE TO DATA: A PIPELINE FOR ARABIC

The transformation of a printed Arabic text into an annotated digital resource involves a series of steps that cannot be considered purely technical, but instead entail significant theoretical and methodological choices. In particular, in the case of texts characterized by linguistic and graphic variation, each stage of the pipeline, from digitization to annotation, contributes to shaping the data and determining its possibilities for analysis and reuse, especially in teaching contexts.

Printed texts and graphic complexity. Printed texts in Arabic present a graphic complexity that reflects both the editorial history of the materials and the linguistic practices underlying their production. Typography, the non uniform use of diacritical marks, the management of graphic variants, and the layout of the text on the page are all elements that significantly affect readability and subsequent digitization, thus constituting a primary source of complexity that impacts the entire pipeline.

² Further information on RĀBIṬA (Resources for Arabic: Bridging Interoperable Texts and Annotation) is available at: <https://github.com/eliguagliotta/RABITA>.

OCR: errors, limits, and choices. The use of OCR technologies represents a crucial step in the digitization process of Arabic texts, but also one of the most critical points in the entire pipeline. In this study, the OCR process is understood not as a simple automatic transcription, but as a generative image to text transduction carried out through a Vision Language Model. Following comparative tests conducted on different systems, QARI was adopted, an Arabic OCR model obtained through fine tuning of the multimodal model Qwen2-VL-2B-Instruct (Wasfy et al., 2025). This choice departs from traditional deterministic OCR approaches, favoring a model capable of integrating visual information and linguistic generation, particularly suited to materials characterized by heterogeneous scan quality and strong graphic variability. The adoption of a generative OCR system, however, introduces new types of errors that do not concern only the recognition of graphemes, but also the handling of word boundaries, the reproduction of repetitive sequences, or potential interference between writing systems (see Examples 1, 2, and 3, Sec. 4). For this reason, the choice of the OCR model and of the generation parameters, as well as pre and post processing strategies, takes on a central methodological value. These decisions directly affect the final representation of the linguistic data and the possibility of making visible, or conversely attenuating, phenomena of variation and language contact that constitute an integral part of the texts under analysis.

Normalization and annotation. The normalization and annotation phase is the stage at which the tensions between standardization and fidelity to the text become most evident. The texts obtained from the OCR phase are first subjected to automatic linguistic annotation carried out through CamelParser (Elshabrawy et al., 2023), a system based on CAMEL Tools (Obeid et al., 2020) that enables morphological analysis and POS tagging of texts in Arabic script, interpreted according to the morphological model of Modern Standard Arabic while also recognizing lexical and morphological forms typical of dialectal varieties, thus generating an output compliant with the UD scheme. The adoption of UD responds to the need to ensure interoperability, comparability, and reuse of the data, situating the produced resources within widely shared annotation ecosystems. The output of the automatic annotation, exported in CoNLL-U format, is subsequently imported into the INCEPTION infrastructure (Klie et al., 2018), where a phase of manual validation and refinement of the annotation takes place, including the addition of further annotation layers oriented toward teaching purposes. However, applying such standards to Arabic texts characterized by graphic and linguistic variation entails mediating between the requirements of the standard and the linguistic reality of the text (see Fig. 1, Sec. 4). From a pedagogically oriented perspective, these choices acquire additional significance, as they determine the type of access to the text offered to students and the way in which linguistic complexity is either made visible or, conversely, attenuated.

4. CASE STUDY: *WĀLD FAḌĪLA*

The case study selected for this analysis is *Wald Faḍīla*, a narrative text published by Amira Charfeddine in 2019, which addresses issues of identity, social marginalization, and the normative control of bodies and subjectivities, with particular attention to gender dynamics and the stigma associated with sexuality (Achour, 2022). *Wald Faḍīla* is particularly well suited to highlighting the challenges discussed in the previous sections. The text displays a linguistic and stylistic stratification that reflects the colloquial discursive practices of contemporary Tunis, positioning itself beyond the conventional boundary between norm and usage, and between standard variety and marked linguistic forms, traditionally drawn in the selection of materials for university teaching contexts. From a linguistic perspective, *Wald Faḍīla* shows a marked presence of orthographic and morphosyntactic variation, as well as alternation between registers and urban varieties. The use of code-switching, together with the emergence of sociolinguistically marked features such as profanity, contributes to the creation of a heterogeneous textual fabric that is not a marginal element of the text, but a structural component of its narrative construction and communicative function. The application of OCR tools to a text of this kind makes particularly evident the limitations of OCR technologies for Arabic. Linguistic sequences that diverge from expected forms tend to generate a high number of errors that cannot be reduced to simple graphic inaccuracies, but instead affect segmentation, readability, and, in some cases, the interpretability of the text. In particular, phenomena of variation and code-switching are often rendered inadequately, with effects that compromise the possibility of subsequent coherent linguistic annotation, as illustrated by the following examples.

(1) I came to warn you about your son Fadel. (p. 18)

Original Text

- شو، راو جيتك بش نطقك على فاضل ولدك .

OCR output

- شو، راو جيتك بش نطقك على فاضل ول .dek

Segmented text

شو راو جيتك-ك بش ن-فطن-ك على فاضل ولد-ك

Glosses

2SG.F-son Fadel PREP 2SG.F-warn-1SG FUT 2SG.F-come.PFV.1SG PRAG INTJ

(2) Oh, poor mother, he has killed himself! (p.24)

Original Text

- يا ميمتبيييبي إنتحر!

OCR output

- يا ميمتبييريبي إنتحر!

Segmented Text

يا ميمت-بي إنتحر

Glosses

suicide.PFV.3SG.M 1SG.POSS-Mother.DIM VOC

(3) Oh Lord! He has thrown himself down, it's over! (p.24)

Original Text

- يا لطيف رمى روحو سايبى!

OCR output

- يا لط ϩϣ رمى روحو سايبى!

Segmented Text

يا لطيف رمى روح-و سايبى

Glosses

PRAG.FR self-3SG.M throw.PFV.3SG.M INTJ.RELIG VOC

In Ex. 1, we observe that during the OCR phase part of the text is transduced into Latin characters (*dek*). This error can be traced back to incorrect segmentation and graphic confusion, generating a token with no linguistic status. This type of error compromises the identification of morphemic boundaries and, consequently, syntactic and semantic annotation. Ex. 2 shows a different but equally significant case. The OCR reproduces the lengthening typical of writing that mimics orality. However, additional Arabic graphemes are introduced that do not correspond to the original text. Ex. 3 highlights how the OCR system produces a sequence of characters in the Cyrillic alphabet (*ϩϣ* /if/) instead of a correct rendering in Arabic script. This type of error cannot be attributed to graphemic confusion within the writing system adopted for the novel, but rather signals a more radical failure in the script identification process, with the uncontrolled shift to a set of characters belonging to a different graphic domain. By contrast, it is noteworthy that the element *سايبى* a borrowing from French (*ça y est*), is recognized by the OCR as an integral part of the Arabic text. This observation leads to the subsequent stage of text processing, namely linguistic annotation, which raises important methodological questions.

For the project, the INCEPTION infrastructure was adopted, as it allows the integration of different POS formalisms and supports, among others, the UD scheme, which is the same annotation framework used for the automatic annotation performed with CamelParser. This continuity between automatic annotation and the revision environment makes it possible to frame manual annotation as a process of validation and refinement of the data. This operational simplification does not eliminate, but rather makes more visible, the theoretical choices involved in adopting a standardized annotation scheme such as UD. In particular, the need to map the data onto predefined formal categories creates tension between the abstract representation of the text and fidelity to its linguistic and discursive specificities. Colloquial elements and hybrid or mixed language sequences require compromise solutions that make complexity explicit without sacrificing the internal coherence of the annotation scheme. In this sense, the text becomes a testing ground for reflecting on the limits and possibilities of existing standards when applied to non-standard materials.

Fig. 1 illustrates the methodology adopted during the manual validation and annotation phase of the text. First, the pragmatic particle *تي* initially associated with a fallback value (NOAN),³ is reinterpreted as an interjection (INTJ), making its discursive and interactional role visible. This type of intervention is particularly significant, as it shows how INCEPTION allows the standard annotation scheme to be complemented by a context sensitive reading, without compromising the overall coherence of the annotation and while retaining the NOAN tag as a marker of non-standard elements. Second, the POS (in orange), the lemma (in light blue), and the conjugated form (in green) of the Tunisian verb *تخافش* (where the final grapheme constitutes the second element of the circumfix negation *mā-VERB-š*) are corrected and complemented by the verbal root (in purple),⁴ thus resolving the ambiguity left unresolved during the automatic annotation phase.

Figure 1: Annotation of an excerpt from *Wald Faḍīla* in the INCEPTION environment. The sentence means: "Come on, do not be afraid, it is written in destiny!" At the top, the output of the automatic annotation. At the bottom, the same sentence after validation and manual intervention.

Finally, the French sequence *ça y est*, automatically handled as a series of isolated tokens and associated with residual categories (X), is reanalyzed according to its pragmatic function in context. These interventions make explicit an interpretive choice that automatic annotation, by its very nature, is unable to perform when dealing with texts that are so noisy and heterogeneous. In support of this claim, it is sufficient to note that *ça y est* appears elsewhere in the text written in Arabic characters (سايي), revealing the absence of a consistent orthographic treatment of borrowings within the text itself. This graphic oscillation further highlights the difficulty of establishing a clear boundary between what can be considered a borrowing that has become integrated into the language and what continues to be perceived as an exogenous insertion, thereby challenging annotation approaches based on a binary distinction between native and foreign forms. From a pedagogical perspective, such ambiguities do not represent a limitation but rather a resource. The visualization of the annotation allows students to engage with the gradual and negotiated nature of lexical integration processes, as well as with the role played by orthographic and annotation choices in the construction of meaning. In this sense, annotation does not merely structure linguistic data, but becomes a mediating tool that makes the complexity of non-canonical texts explicit and encourages critical reflection on the limits and possibilities of existing standards when applied to linguistically and culturally situated materials. *Wald Faḍīla* thus emerges not only as an object of analysis, but as a teaching resource capable of making the linguistic complexity of Arabic visible and fostering a deeper awareness of the processes involved in constructing textual data in a digital environment.

Indeed, RĀBIṬA resources are designed to function as dynamic pedagogical tools. A pilot phase of classroom implementation is planned for the upcoming academic year. For instance, students may be invited to work directly on OCR outputs, comparing them with the original printed text in order to identify recognition errors and reflect on their linguistic and graphic causes. This activity allows learners to engage critically with the notion of "error", shifting from a prescriptive perspective to an analytical one. A second type of activity focuses on annotation. Using the INCEPTION environment, students may be asked

³ The NOAN label is a "No Analysis" marker generated during text processing with CamelParser. This tag highlights categorization difficulties and signals lexically problematic segments. Such labels can be useful in the exploratory analysis of the text to identify points of linguistic variation or parsing errors. By contrast, X is an official POS category in the UD scheme, used to indicate elements classified as other or unclassified.

⁴ The root was also added for the noun مكتوب "destiny".

to validate or revise automatically generated annotations, particularly in cases involving colloquial forms, code-switching, or pragmatically marked elements. This task is expected to encourage reflection on the limits of standardized annotation schemes such as Universal Dependencies and to highlight the interpretive dimension of linguistic analysis. Finally, selected excerpts from the corpus can be used for task-based activities, such as role-play or guided rewriting, where students must reformulate linguistically complex or hybrid sequences into different registers or varieties. In this way, the annotated text becomes a mediating object that connects computational analysis, linguistic awareness, and communicative practice.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND PERSPECTIVES

This contribution has offered a methodological reflection on digital textual practices applied to complex Arabic texts, highlighting how the transition from the printed page to annotated data cannot be reduced to a sequence of technical operations, but involves interpretive choices with significant implications for teaching. Through the analysis of a pipeline integrating digitization, OCR, and linguistic annotation, it has been shown how the graphic and linguistic complexity of Arabic texts constitutes both a critical challenge and an epistemic resource for the teaching of language, culture, and literature. The case study discussed has concretely illustrated the limitations of currently available computational tools when applied to materials characterized by variation, code-switching, and non-standard features. These limitations have not been interpreted as mere technological shortcomings, but rather as indicators of the tensions between standardization, data representation, and fidelity to the linguistic reality of the text. In this sense, the adoption of shared annotation schemes such as Universal Dependencies appears not as a definitive solution, but as a space of methodological negotiation requiring constant critical reflection. From a forward-looking perspective, the reflections presented here open the way to further developments both at the methodological and applied levels. The extension of the analysis to additional texts and genres, the experimentation with alternative OCR and annotation strategies, and the construction of interoperable and reusable digital resources are part of an ongoing research trajectory of which this contribution presents an initial methodological application. These developments contribute to fostering a closer dialogue between Digital Humanities, computational linguistics, and the teaching of Arabic, placing digital textuality at the center of educational practices attentive to linguistic complexity and the long-term sustainability of resources.

Beyond its methodological and pedagogical implications, the RĀBIṬA project also contributes to public engagement by promoting access to linguistically complex Arabic texts and making the processes underlying their digital transformation visible to a broader audience. By publishing annotated resources in open-access formats and designing their integration into teaching and training activities, the project fosters a critical awareness of how language technologies operate, their limitations, and their interpretive dimension. In this sense, RĀBIṬA does not only produce data, but also encourages forms of digital literacy that are particularly relevant in the context of under-resourced languages, where technological mediation often remains opaque or inaccessible.

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